

African Universities: Translating Francophone Campus Forms

Ruth Bush

University of Bristol, Bristol, UK

ruth.bush@bristol.ac.uk

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13696815.2024.2334692>

This special issue is the third instalment in the “Campus Forms” series published in *Journal of African Cultural Studies*. The first, edited by Anne W. Gulick, considers cultural expressions of the university as “an idea, an institution and a physical space” (2023, 1) across different cultural forms. The fascinating range of contributions in that issue affirms the multiplicity of campus forms on the African continent, moving far beyond the narrow confines of the principally North American and British genre of campus fiction. Across geographies, these articles place particular emphasis on love stories, fantasies and realities of what it means to be a student, and the many registers of protest found in and around universities. The second special issue, edited by Carli Coetzee and Louise Egbunike (2023), presents campus forms in Lagos and other Nigerian higher education contexts, showing how a wide range of “interstitial” (Olaniyan 2018) intellectual reflections on conditions of knowledge production in Nigeria have built from the thriving academic community of the Lagos Studies Association.

The present bilingual (French–English) issue considers cultural representations of universities and related pedagogical innovations across the diverse national contexts of Senegal, Côte d’Ivoire, Benin and Cameroon. Debates pertaining to the use of French, the socio-political valency of institutionalised Francophonie, and economic and military injustices of *la Françafrique* continue to resound in popular and intellectual discourse (Borrel et al. 2021; Elgas 2023; Chafer and Majumdar 2023). Accordingly, the term “Francophone” is used with circumspection here to connect these densely multilingual university contexts where “Frenches” mingle with Wolof, Nouchi, Fongbe, Yoruba, Camfranglais and many other tongues. These universities remain porous theatres for protest and debate, as witnessed most recently in the June 2023 violence in Senegal. Highly politicised dynamics play out, from the selection of staff by the ruling President to the role of unions and the powerful regional regulatory body, the Conseil Africain et Malgache pour l’Enseignement Supérieur (CAMES)

(Cissé 2018). The autonomy of these public universities is highly relative. The role of the university in producing meaningful knowledge and nurturing forms of social relation which are appropriate for the challenges of the present and decades ahead is an ever-present question.

In response, this issue emerges from an ongoing conversation between colleagues at the Université Cheikh Anta Diop (Senegal), Université Félix Houphouët-Boigny (Côte d'Ivoire), Université d'Abomey-Calavi (Benin) and Université Yaoundé I (Cameroon). This is part of a collective project, "AFRIUNI: The Creative Lives of African Universities project: pedagogies of hope and despair".¹ Our project team consists of 11 researchers across these four countries: three research associates (Monique Kwachou, Finagnon André Gaga and Alain Serge Agnessan) and seven international collaborators (Bacary Sarr, Marie-Clémence Adom, Fernand Nouwligbèto, Romain Dédjinnaki Hounzandji, Valentine Ubanako, Roger Fopa Kuete and Albert Jiatsa Jokeng). This participatory project invites a larger network of students, staff and stakeholders external to the university to reflect critically on the university as an idea, institution and concrete reality. Our (non-)methodological emphasis is on bottom-up forms of creative endeavour (including literature, film, hip-hop, visual art and theatre, as well as everyday *débrouillardise* or resourcefulness) in the archived, present-day and imagined future lives of these universities. Initial planning and development workshops took place at the Université Cheikh Anta Diop and Université Yaoundé I in 2019. Further workshops were held in Dakar in February 2022, Bristol in June 2023, and Yaoundé in October 2023, together with online events in March and October 2021. A conference took place in Abomey-Calavi (Benin) in January 2024, together with a series of participatory workshops with students across all four universities which are in progress at the time of writing.

This special issue is also partly a result of online communication breakthroughs (and occasional breakdowns) catalysed by the Covid-19 pandemic. The papers were presented during an online panel at the African Literature Association (USA) in 2021, then developed during online study days held during lockdown in October 2021, as well as in the various workshops outlined above. The online study days brought together students, staff and creative writers from Senegal, Cameroon, Côte d'Ivoire and Benin to reflect on immediate experiences of teaching literature under Covid (the results were later published in the *Journal of the African Literature Association*) and broader issues of university life (see Fopa Kuete

2022). They closed with a conversation between François Nkémé, author of the campus novel *Le Cimetière des bacheliers* (2008), and Cilas Kemedjio, academic and author of an important testimony of the 1990 student strikes in Yaoundé (2013). That conversation was a reminder of the capacity of literary texts to generate and archive a language – in this case, many Camfranglais terms and expressions – capable of expressing the tragic arc of the young student protagonist’s experience on campus, from the claustrophobia of a jampacked lecture theatre to the panicked dash for an elusive toilet and a spiral into despair (see also Adebisi 2017; Omotayo 2023).

The AFRIUNI project is a cog in the much larger and longer-term discussion concerning the ethics and politics of knowledge production in the wake of European colonialism and neoliberal structural adjustment policies (Federici, Caffentzis and Alidou 2000).

“Knowledge” here includes the inheritance, appropriation and reinvention of research methodologies and disciplinary silos according to institutional practices (degree programmes, student orientation, government agendas, processes of Africanisation, international development policy). “Knowledge” also includes the kinds of improvised, everyday and creative *know-how* produced by staff and students faced with the chronic infrastructural pressures of overcrowding, limited investment in student housing and teaching facilities, contested curricular reforms (transition to the *licence–master–doctorat* system in particular), and gendered violence or discrimination that characterise university lives. Within the AFRIUNI project, we are especially attentive to the dynamics of Africanisation and decolonisation as they have played out historically in the curricula across these four institutions. We seek to consider the place and pace of literature and humanities education more broadly within these dynamics, given the huge and growing number of students studying humanities disciplines, sustaining debates over their perceived value in producing democratic citizens and the risks of generating critical thought in postcolonial autocracies. Mindful of the many potential pitfalls of funded research collaborations of this nature (set out most recently in the “Africa Charter on Transformative Research Collaborations”²), we hope to contribute to the ongoing critical examination of university life in relation to broader interconnected issues concerning anti-intellectualism and neo-liberalism, Africanisation and globalisation, Francophobia and Anglophilia.

The articles that follow consider a range of related themes including academic freedom and censorship, sexual harassment and pan-African and decolonial temporalities. They explore

the capacity of art (visual, literary, performance, filmic) to give imaginative – and at times *transformative* – form to such realities. Articles by Fernand Nouwligbèto and Romain Dédjinnaki Hounzandji discuss the role that theatre plays in their teaching at the Université d’Abomey-Calavi. They consider specific examples of how creative pedagogy, through co-created theatre performance and analysis of theatrical texts, has equipped students with tools to reflect on the possibilities and barriers to critical thinking in the university classroom. This first-hand documentation of scenes of teaching is an important contribution to the extant discussion of academic freedoms (Diouf and Mamdani 1994; Sall and Mangu 2005), while acknowledging student lethargy, as well as audience agency. A third contribution from Benin, by Opèoluwa Blandine Agbaka, considers the marginalisation of the arts in Beninese higher education, and the corresponding efforts to create a structured vocational programme in arts and culture at the Université d’Abomey-Calavi. With ongoing headlines concerning the restitution of African art works, this initiative strives to incorporate local artistic knowledge and practices into a viable and meaningful training programme for university students. Two articles, by Marie-Clémence Adom and Albert Jiatsa Jokeng, focus explicitly on the generic form given to university lives through poetry/performance and the short story. Adom’s article draws on the extensive Francophone scholarship on *zouglou*, a poetic-musical form that took hold on the campus of Cocody, before reaching mass audiences. With detailed attention to language and reception, the article unpicks the poetic complexity of campus critique. Albert Jiatsa Jokeng’s analysis of the representation of sexual harassment in short stories emphasises the capacity of that condensed form to speak of injustices on campus to particular local readerships. Lastly, my article, co-written with Bacary Sarr, considers the contradictions of Cheikh Anta Diop’s inscription in the imagination of university life in Senegal, drawing on fiction, film and student-led movements. The complexity of student subjectivities and temporal entanglement expressed through these “campus forms” belies any reduction of Senegalese university life to linear dynamics of decolonisation and presents instead a porous and future-oriented concept of Africanisation.

At a time when artificial intelligence tools such as ChatGPT, Grammarly and QuillBot, as well as neural machine translation services such as DeepL, are reinventing the way that complex ideas are expressed, it is worth reflecting on the historical, linguistic and cultural contingency of academic writing traditions. Building this project and the translations of the articles that followed has evoked familiar contrasts between Anglophone and Francophone academic traditions. Moreover, it raises questions regarding the kinds of journal work

required to overcome the barriers to knowledge dissemination that such traditions have partly sustained on the African continent.³ Such journal work includes academic writing workshops, academic translation workshops, and commitments from journal editors, copyeditors, proofreaders, publishers and funders to support multilingual publications. The preparation of this special issue, with its process of peer review and translation, has highlighted vocabularies, readerly assumptions (e.g. a Francophone tendency towards abstraction), practices of academic knowledge production, and their translational challenges. The very term “academic journal”, translated to the French “*revue scientifique*”, formalises knowledge production and circulation in relation to the academy and its codes. Where Francophone contexts have a significant history of radical creative and intellectual periodicals, including *Présence Africaine*, *Abbia* and *Revue noire*, divergences in academic (or *scientific*, to calque the French term) writing style and formal conventions between English and French remain. This speaks to the intricacy of linguistic divides, encoded in academic practices that might also be termed postcolonial realms of memory (Achille, Forsdick and Moudileno 2020). Francophone academic writing – broadly speaking – has inherited French modes of methodological rigour and “scientificity”. It is common to find theses of over 800 pages (whereas Anglophone theses might more commonly be 300–400 pages), structured in numbered sections, subsections and sub-subsections. Such numbering has been removed from some of the articles translated from French in this special issue. These contrasts also include the heritage of academic traditions found in degree structures, academic rituals (e.g. the predominance of oral examination in Francophone contexts, and closed PhD vivas versus public *soutenances*), citational patterns (e.g. the significance of figures such as Lilyan Kesteloot, Mohamadou Kane or Jean-Pierre Olivier de Sardan), intellectual traditions, and referencing systems (the structure and role of bibliographies and indexes), and extend down to the structure of an essay, paragraph and sentence which gives form to academic arguments.

The aim of this very short introduction is not to present a value judgement of either body of work (and, of course, there are many exceptions to the broad differences sketched out above). Rather, I wish to highlight the kinds of formal and institutional challenges that exist in the translation of academic knowledge on the continent between two of the major vehicular languages: French and English. Attending to pluriversal, multilingual knowledges, especially those residing in African languages, remains a priority and reveals the intricacies of knowledge circulation through translation (or untranslatability). Yet there are also evident disjunctures and lags within academic contexts and a political-economic-technological world

system where English remains dominant in relation to other colonial languages.⁴ Resisting this linguistic dominance within academic publishing requires commitment and, ultimately, funding. Publishing dual versions of the articles (each with a distinct DOI) in the present special issue was enabled by a funding stream (in this case a European Research Council project grant) which paid the translators according to recommended rates. Where funding is available, publishing a bilingual issue (especially one originating from an English-language journal and publisher) means that articles *can* circulate in parallel across different intellectual spaces, despite enduring linguistic striations and the academic cultural divides. Publishing dual versions is a way to ensure that knowledge circulates across linguistic borders. Yet the system is far from perfect, not least in the current transitional phase towards fully Open Access publishing. The Open Access article processing charge (currently around £2,500 or 1.8 million CFA francs per article, which is approximately four times the basic monthly salary of a university lecturer in Cameroon) remains prohibitive for most authors based on the African continent, where so-called “read & publish” or “transformative” agreements rarely exist between publishers and universities (especially Francophone universities).⁵ In what follows, our bilingual issue aims first to generate critical dialogue and greater understanding of Francophone university contexts on the continent. More broadly, this contribution is part of current efforts to confront the refracted effect of the global academic publishing environment, notably its Open Access policies and Anglophone bias, on African scholarship.

Acknowledgements

This article is part of a project that has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement no. 949378).

References

Aboderin, I., Fuh, D., Balcha Gebremariam, E., and Segalo, P. 2023. “Beyond ‘equitable partnerships’: the imperative of transformative research collaborations with Africa.” *Global Social Challenges Journal* 2 (2): 212–228.

Achille, Etienne, Charles Forsdick, and Lydie Moudileno. 2020. *Postcolonial Realms of Memory: Sites and Symbols in Modern France*. Liverpool: Liverpool University Press.

- Adebisi, Foluke. 2017. "Global University Rankings and Toilets." *African Skies*, 28 March. Accessed 10 October 2023. <https://folukeafrica.com/global-university-rankings-toilets/>.
- Borrel, Thomas, Amzat Boukari-Yabara, Benoît Collombat, and Thomas Deltombe (eds). 2021. *Une histoire de la Françafrique*. Paris: Éditions du Seuil.
- Chafer, Tony, and Margaret A. Majumdar (eds). 2023. *Routledge Handbook of Francophone Africa*. London: Routledge.
- Cissé, Chikouna. 2018. *Le CAMES 1968–2018. Un demi-siècle au service de l'enseignement supérieur et de la recherche en Afrique*. Quebec: Éditions Science et Bien Commun.
- Coetzee, Carli. 2018. "Unsettling the Air-Conditioned Room: Journal Work as Ethical Labour." *Journal of the African Literature Association* 12 (2): 101–115.
- Coetzee, Carli, and Louisa Uchum Egbunike. 2023. "Nigerian Campus Forms." *Journal of African Cultural Studies* 35 (3): 249–253.
- Diouf, Mamadou, and Mahmood Mamdani. 1994. *Liberté académique en Afrique*. Dakar: CODESRIA.
- Elgas. 2023. *Les Bons Ressentiments. Essai sur le malaise post-colonial*. Paris: Riveneuve.
- Federici, Silvia Constantine, George Caffentzis, and Ousseina Alidou. 2000. *A Thousand Flowers: Social Struggles against Structural Adjustment in African Universities*. Trenton NJ: Africa World Press.
- Fopa Kuete, Roger (ed.). 2022. "Notes from the Field: Teaching African Literature in Covid Times/Enseignement et pratiques de la littérature dans les universités africaines à l'ère de Covid." *Journal of the African Literature Association* 16 (2): 363–385.
- Gulick, Anne W. 2023. "Introduction to Campus Forms." *Journal of African Cultural Studies* 35 (1): 1–6.
- Kemedjio, Cilas. 2013. *Mémoires des Années de Braise: La Grève Estudiantine de 1991 Expliquée*. Yaoundé: Éditions Terroirs.
- Nkémé, François. 2008. *Le Cimetière des Bacheliers*. 3rd ed. Yaoundé: Ifrikiya/Proximité.

Olaniyan, Tejumola. 2018. "The Affirmative, the Interstitial: Biodun Jeyifo and an Inventory of Postcolonial Theory and Criticism." *Journal of the African Literature Association* 12 (1): 1–7.

Omotayo, Kolawole Charles. 2023. "'Shot-putting' and Other Dirty Secrets: Nigerian Students' Everyday Struggles." *Journal of African Cultural Studies* 35 (3): 326–332.

Sall, Ebrima, and André Mbata Bekutumesu Mangu. 2005. "Introduction: The Quest for Academic Freedom Today." *Journal of Higher Education in Africa / Revue de l'Enseignement Supérieur en Afrique* 3 (2): 1–16.

Sapiro, Gisèle, and Hélène Seiler-Juilleret. 2023. "Éditer les sciences humaines et sociales à l'heure de la globalisation et du numérique." *Biens Symboliques / Symbolic Goods* 12: 1–12.

¹ See the project website at <https://afriuniproject.blogs.bristol.ac.uk/>.

² See <https://bpb-eu-w2.wpmucdn.com/blogs.bristol.ac.uk/dist/1/627/files/2023/07/Africa-Charter-for-Transformative-Collaborations.pdf>.

³ On "journal work as ethical labour" in African contexts, see Carli Coetzee (2018).

⁴ For a recent discussion of challenges in academic publishing trends (including Anglophone, especially American, dominance, the high costs associated with Open Access, especially in English- and German-language academic publishing, and resulting threats to autonomy), see Gisèle Sapiro and Hélène Seiler-Juilleret (2023). For a recent overview relating to academic publishing by scholars on the African continent, including the (in)visibility created by the global science indexing system, see Aboderin et al.

⁵ Vouchers exist for Africa-based authors and readers to be able to access some publications through a paywall, creating what appears to be a tiered system since readers based in Northern universities are given direct access through their institutions. Meanwhile, authors in Northern universities, or whose institution is a member of a consortium with a publishing agreement, benefit from the necessary financing system to pay Open Access article processing charges.